

Ethereal Economic Viewpoint of Deen Dayal Upadhyaya

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Abstract

Deendayal Upadhyay envisioned educating people with Indian values. He believed that understanding the integral humanism within Hinduism was crucial for addressing societal issues effectively. Human survival depends on natural resources, and humanism forms the foundation of interactions between individuals and nature. Upadhyay criticized the Western economic structure, arguing that it contradicted natural laws and led to unrest and disasters. He advocated for adopting integral humanism to counteract these negative consequences. According to Upadhyay, developing countries should prioritize agricultural development over rapid industrialization to avoid worsening poverty and unemployment. Achieving self-sufficiency in food grain production is vital, requiring continuous and effective planning in a supportive environment. Neglecting agriculture while promoting industrial growth can have harmful effects, a viewpoint Upadhyay supported.

Keywords Ethereal Economic, Deen Dayal Upadhyay, Economic Views, Holistic Economy, Human Values.

Introduction

During British rule, the Indian economy suffered significant devastation. India's share of the global economy did significantly decrease under British rule. Some estimates put it as high as 27% of world GDP in the early 1700s, shrinking to around 3% by the time of independence. Lack of exports, coupled with devastating famines, painted a bleak economic picture. Rampant grain importation hindered the growth of new businesses, left existing industries in disarray, and worsened the nation's food crisis. Deendayal Upadhyay advocated for India to develop its own economic policies tailored to its unique conditions, needs, and resources, rather than blindly imitating America, Russia, or Europe, given the differing circumstances. He emphasized that boosting people's purchasing power through widespread employment and fair compensation could mitigate social and economic inequalities. Bhartiya Jansangh proposed achieving a minimum standard of living, equitable distribution, and full employment as primary planning goals. Upadhyay envisioned using advanced technologies to empower every household as a productive unit within a decentralized economy, prioritizing employment-oriented initiatives over large-scale industries that require substantial investments.

Recognizing the importance of agricultural self-sufficiency amid rapid industrialization, Upadhyay stressed nurturing small-scale businesses, especially those producing essential daily goods. He emphasized the crucial role of domestic food grain production in ensuring national food security and urged prioritizing the agricultural sector's development. Upadhyay cautioned against blindly following Western development models, highlighting the dangers of neglecting the agricultural sector. He criticized mechanization efforts inspired by Russia and opposed Congress's cooperative farming proposal, asserting the farmers' ownership of their land. Upadhyay's perspective highlighted the importance of economically empowering farmers to boost both agricultural productivity and industrial growth, thus averting potential food supply crises and promoting sustainable economic development tailored to India's unique context.

Objective of study

This study aims to explore and analyze the economic principles and perspectives advocated by Deen Dayal Upadhyaya, a prominent Indian philosopher, economist, and

political thinker. Through a comprehensive examination of Upadhyaya's writings, speeches, and ideological framework, this research seeks to elucidate the ethereal essence of his economic philosophy. By delving into Upadhyaya's views on integral humanism, decentralization, self-reliance, and social justice, the study endeavors to provide valuable insights into his vision for a harmonious and equitable economic order. Through this exploration, the aim is to contribute to a deeper understanding of Upadhyaya's enduring influence on economic thought and policy discourse in contemporary India and beyond.

Review of Literature

Integral Humanism: A Primer by Deendayal Upadhyaya - This would be the foundational text for understanding Upadhyaya's economic viewpoint. It outlines the principles of Integral Humanism, which forms the basis of his socio-economic philosophy.

Indian Economy: Performance and Policies by Uma Kapila - This book provides a comprehensive overview of the Indian economy, including its historical development, current status, and policy framework. Understanding the broader economic context of India can provide insights into how Upadhyaya's ideas fit within the country's economic landscape.

Swadeshi Indology: Decolonizing Sanskrit Knowledge Systems by Rajiv Malhotra - This book discusses the importance of indigenous knowledge systems in India, which aligns with the ethos of Integral Humanism and self-reliance.

Main Text

Agricultural Realm of India

Upadhyaya saw agriculture as the backbone of India's economy and advocated for policies that supported farmers and rural communities. This focus aimed to improve the livelihoods of a majority of Indians and promote balanced development. Agriculture ought to serve as the foundation for development since a significant portion of the population relies on it. Despite this, agriculture has historically not received as much attention as industry. Rather than strengthening its advantages, there has been a tendency to prioritize addressing weaknesses. The crucial link between a robust rural sector and increased demand for manufactured goods has not been fully acknowledged. It's imperative for the government to focus on enhancing the income of rural inhabitants, considering that a large proportion of the population resides there. The primary objective should be to bolster their purchasing power to stimulate economic growth. Furthermore, the interdependence between agriculture and industry is evident, as industry relies on agriculture for raw materials and labor. Education and skill development among the workforce can significantly enhance industrial productivity. Neglecting this aspect when analyzing supply and demand can lead to economic slowdowns and potential closures due to a significant decline in demand. It's essential for farmers to receive fair prices for their produce to improve their livelihoods, boost production, and promote national self-sufficiency. Making farming a profitable venture is crucial for the prosperity of farmers. Setting minimum prices should not only cover production costs but also include a margin for profit, as suggested by Sharma (2017). Deendayalji emphasized the significance of cows and oxen in agriculture, hence the reverence for cows in India. Traditionally, the killing of cows and their offspring has been prohibited in India, although there are exceptions to this rule at present. While the Bharatiya Jansangh opposes the killing of cows and has proposed a constitutional amendment to ban it, other political parties generally support it.

Self-Reliance and Swadeshi

Upadhyaya promoted economic self-reliance for India, advocating for Swadeshi, the use of domestic products and fostering indigenous industries. This aimed to reduce dependence on foreign powers and promote economic independence. He believed that India's economic development should be based on its own resources, culture, and traditions. Upadhyaya believed in simple living and avoiding excessive materialism. This perspective emphasized ethical consumption and reducing dependence on imported goods. He advocated for an economic system that placed importance on individual character and moral development alongside material progress. Upadhyaya's concept of "Antyodaya" (upliftment of the last person) emphasizes moral and ethical considerations in economic development. He believed that economics should serve the well-being of all, not just material gain. This aligns with the concept of ethical economics, which emphasizes values like justice, equity, and sustainability alongside economic efficiency.

Upadhyaya believed in the concept of Dharma, which encompasses righteousness, duty, and moral responsibility. He envisioned an economic system that operates in alignment with Dharma, where economic activities are guided by ethical considerations and serve the common good. Upadhyaya emphasized decentralization of economic power and

promoted the idea of Swadeshi, or self-reliance. He advocated for the development of local economies and indigenous industries to empower communities and reduce dependence on foreign imports. Integral Humanism acknowledges the interdependence between humans and nature. Upadhyaya's economic viewpoint emphasizes the importance of environmental conservation and sustainable development practices to ensure the well-being of present and future generations. Upadhyaya rejected the narrow focus on GDP growth as the sole indicator of progress. He advocated for a more holistic approach to development, which takes into account social, cultural, and spiritual dimensions alongside economic factors.

Holistic Economic Approach

An imbalance in material resources, whether excessive or lacking, can undermine the principles of Dharma. In Western societies, the pursuit of wealth often ensnares individuals, initially viewed as a means to righteous conduct but evolving into an unending quest for pleasure, leading to a cycle of insatiable desire and potentially unethical means of acquisition. Conversely, when material wealth is scarce, it becomes an end in itself, disrupting the balance required for upholding Dharma. To maintain harmony, wealth acquisition should be approached with social consciousness, considering the needs of others and ensuring ethical methods. While the West's economic ideologies may seem universally applicable, India's unique economic conditions and cultural values necessitate distinct developmental approaches, emphasizing social duties and collective stewardship alongside individual rights. Reform efforts should blend tradition with innovation to drive progress while preserving core values, aiming for a synthesis of materialism and spiritualism. The ideological clash between socialism and capitalism should not overshadow the significance of individual responsibility and ethical conduct. Development plans should prioritize diversity, work-life balance, and holistic well-being to prevent dehumanization. Harmonizing material and spiritual pursuits is crucial for societal progress and individual fulfillment, requiring a humanistic framework that integrates all aspects of human life. Technology should be utilized judiciously, promoting humanistic values and incorporating grassroots perspectives. Governments should prioritize citizen welfare, respecting indigenous cultures and traditions. Society should not solely focus on consumption but also emphasize sacrifice and contentment. Hinduism, with its adaptable yet timeless principles, offers a framework for societal sustenance, emphasizing universal coexistence and peace. Happiness transcends material wealth, guided by the principles of Dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksha, which prioritize ethical conduct, harmonious progress, and detachment from material outcomes. Fulfillment of basic needs is essential for understanding and practicing Dharma, highlighting the interconnectedness of Dharma, Artha, and Kama. Excessive focus on the state over culture and individuals should be avoided to maintain societal balance. Upadhyaya recognized the spiritual dimension of wealth and cautioned against the excessive pursuit of materialism. He emphasized the importance of inner enrichment and spiritual fulfillment alongside material prosperity, advocating for a balanced approach to economic development.

Key Tenets of Ethereal Economic Viewpoint

1. Dharma-based Economics: Upadhyaya emphasized the importance of aligning economic activities with the principles of Dharma or righteousness. According to him, economic policies should be guided by moral values such as honesty, compassion, and social responsibility. He argued that economic progress devoid of ethical considerations leads to moral degradation and societal disintegration.

2. Decentralized Economy: Upadhyaya advocated for a decentralized economic model that empowers local communities and promotes self-sufficiency. He believed that excessive centralization of economic power leads to inequality and exploitation. Instead, he proposed the concept of "Economic Democracy," wherein decision-making power is decentralized to the grassroots level, enabling people to have a greater say in economic matters.

3. Sarvodaya: The principle of Sarvodaya, meaning the welfare of all, is central to Upadhyaya's economic philosophy. He envisioned an economic system where the benefits of development reach the marginalized sections of society, ensuring inclusive growth and social justice. Upadhyaya emphasized the need to uplift the downtrodden and empower the weakest sections of society through targeted welfare measures and affirmative action.

4. Sustainable Development: Upadhyaya recognized the importance of environmental sustainability in economic development. He advocated for a harmonious relationship between humans and nature, rejecting the notion of unlimited exploitation of natural resources for economic gain. His vision of sustainable development emphasizes the need to preserve ecological balance and protect the environment for future generations.

Relevance in Contemporary Context

1. The ethereal economic viewpoint of Deen Dayal Upadhyaya holds significant relevance in the contemporary context, especially amidst the challenges posed by globalization, environmental degradation, and widening socioeconomic disparities. Several aspects of Upadhyaya's economic philosophy resonate with contemporary debates on inclusive growth, sustainable development, and ethical governance.

2. Inclusive Growth: In an era marked by growing income inequality and social unrest, Upadhyaya's emphasis on Sarvodaya and economic democracy offers valuable insights for policymakers seeking to promote inclusive growth. By prioritizing the welfare of marginalized communities and empowering local stakeholders, his approach can help address the root causes of poverty and inequality.

3. Sustainable Development: The urgency of addressing environmental concerns and transitioning towards sustainable development has never been greater. Upadhyaya's holistic perspective, which integrates ecological considerations with economic policies, provides a roadmap for achieving sustainable development without compromising future generations' well-being.

4. Ethical Governance: Amidst widespread disillusionment with traditional models of governance, Upadhyaya's emphasis on dharma-based economics underscores the importance of ethical leadership and governance. By infusing moral values into economic decision-making processes, policymakers can foster greater trust, accountability, and integrity in public institutions.

Implications for Socioeconomic Development

Embracing Upadhyaya's ethereal economic viewpoint can have profound implications for socioeconomic development, both at the national and global levels. By prioritizing human welfare, environmental sustainability, and ethical governance, his philosophy offers a framework for building a more just, equitable, and harmonious society.

1. Human-Centric Development: Upadhyaya's emphasis on Integral Humanism shifts the focus of development discourse from mere economic indicators to the overall well-being and fulfillment of human potential. By prioritizing human dignity and empowerment, policymakers can design policies and programs that uplift the most vulnerable sections of society and enhance overall quality of life.

2. Community Empowerment: The decentralized economic model advocated by Upadhyaya fosters community empowerment and grassroots participation in decision-making processes. By devolving power to local communities, policymakers can promote inclusive development that is responsive to the diverse needs and aspirations of different regions and social groups.

3. Environmental Stewardship: Upadhyaya's ecological worldview underscores the interconnectedness between human beings and the natural world. By adopting sustainable development practices and promoting environmental stewardship, policymakers can mitigate the adverse impacts of climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation, ensuring a more resilient and livable planet for future generations.

Conclusion

He presumed a scenario devoid of both poverty and excessive wealth, emphasizing the necessity for diligent work to sustain oneself. His concept of excess wealth encompassed an overemphasis on property ownership. He contended that extreme disparities in wealth were not conducive to the healthy progression of society. Rather, he advocated for economic endeavors focused on fulfilling basic needs rather than generating artificial ones, particularly if such pursuits would contribute to heightened consumption. Such unchecked economic growth fosters a culture of consumerism, which tends to spawn social unrest and ultimately exacerbates crime rates. It is posited that a fulfilling life entails the dissolution of unbridled desires and cravings, as unrestrained hunger and greed pervade society. In this milieu, individuals are commodified, with skills and human values often overlooked in favor of sales tactics. This spiritual void engenders insatiable lust for food, power,

possessions, or sex, which is deemed inhumane and detrimental. Therefore, the pursuit of a pure and contented life is advocated as an antidote to such moral degradation. Overall, Upadhyaya's economic viewpoint can be seen as an ethereal or idealistic one, prioritizing human well-being and ethical considerations over purely materialistic goals.

References

1. Anant KS. Pandit Deendayal Upadhyay Vichaar Darshan-ekatm Arthneeti. Vol. 4. New Delhi: Suruchi Prakashan; 2016.
2. Kartik MS. Deendayal Upadhyay Thoughts Revisited Contemporary India. New Delhi: Kunal Books; 2015.
3. Nene VV. Pandit Deendayal Upadhyay Ideology and Perception: Integral Humanism. New Delhi: Suruchi Prakashan; 2010.
4. Sharma SR. Life and Works of Pandit Deendayal Upadhyay. Jaipur: Books Enclave; 2017.
5. Chandra SM. Deendayal Upadhyay Sampoon Vangmay. Vol. 10. New Delhi: Prabhat Prakashan; 2016.
6. Vivasvan S. Pandit Deendayal Upadhyay's Roadmap for India. Partridge India; 2016.
7. Deendayal U. The Two Plans. New Delhi: Prabhat Prakashan; 2015.
8. Deendayal U. Integral Humanism: An Analysis of Some Basic Elements. New Delhi: Prabhat Prakashan; 2020.
9. Singh S, Sharma GD, Bawa J. A review paper on integral humanism: Comparison of Deendayal Upadhyay and his counterparts. Int Journal Multidisciplinary Acad Res 2018
10. Complete Works of Deendayal Upadhyaya, New Delhi: Prabhat Prakashan; 2019 ISBN-10 : 9353222966